

Information sheet 2.05

Certified and approved premises

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

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A. Description of the RRO

Mandatory/voluntary certification/approval of premises is a process including a set of procedures and of actions implemented by producers, conditioners and traders contributing to ensure the phytosanitary compliance of consignments. It can be a part of a larger system maintained by the NPPO in order to guarantee the fulfilment of plant health requirements of plants and plant products intended for trade.

Key property of certified or approved premises is the traceability of activities and tasks (and their components) inherent the pursued phytosanitary objective. Traceability aims to provide access to all trustful pieces of information that may help to prove the compliance of consignments with phytosanitary requirements of importing countries. Requirements on traceability of consignments, in particular their identity and phytosanitary security through all stages of production, handling and transport, are mentioned in ISPM 7 (2011) in the context of procedures connected to the phytosanitary certification system for export. In the case of internal EU movement, the current phytosanitary framework (Articles 6, 10 and 12 of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC¹) requires the establishment of official registers for the identification of producers for whom the official examination shall be carried out. These checks lead to the delivery of plant passports for plants and plant products regulated in internal movement and of specific plant passports for consignments of specified plants and plant products intended for movement to or within a protected zone (see information sheet 2.04 Phytosanitary Certificate and Plant Passport).

The concept of certified or approved premises involves the implementation of official inspection aimed at the verification of the fulfilment of specific requirements. Some examples can be found in the Annexes of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC (paragraph E. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO).

The new regulatory plant health framework² will strengthen the requirements for officially registered and approved premises. In the draft proposal of regulation, an entire chapter is dedicated to the registration of professional operators and traceability in activities of planting, growing, and producing and trading including introduction into and movement within the Union territory, export and sales through distance contracts.

In the context of the new regulatory framework, authorised professional operators may issue plant passports under the supervision of the national competent authority. This increased role of professional operators will be possible only on the condition of obligatory monitoring and traceability of critical points in production and movement processes. Authorised operators shall also ensure that the staff in charge of plant health examinations is competent in doing this task. Operators may put in place phytosanitary

¹ Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8 May 2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organism harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

² Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on protective measures against pests of plants of 6 May 2013. Available from: <http://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2015/12/18-plant-health/>

risk management plans setting out measures implemented to fulfil their obligations. These documents may include instruction manuals describing how operators shall evaluate and mitigate the risk associated with the critical points of their activities. When approved by the competent authority, these plans may lead to an adaptation of the control procedure (e.g. reduction of the frequency) to be carried out by the competent authorities.

B. Risk factors

Table 1. Points of application of measures

Points where measures may be effective		Premises of the place of production (step E1) [m1] Multiplication factor changing the abundance of the pest before leaving the place of production	Premises of processing companies and traders in the Country of production [m3] Multiplication factor changing the abundance from sub-step E1 (when leaving the place of production) to sub-step E2 (before crossing the border of the export country)	Premises of traders and processing companies at destination [m7] Multiplication factor changing the abundance from sub-step E4 (after leaving the point of entry) to sub-step E5 (transferring to the host) in the different scenarios
RRO	Certified or approved premises	X	X	X

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

A full traceability (i.e. all steps and operations made entirely traceable) is a key issue for this RRO that also involves the implementation of specific technical and organisational procedures and the realisation of checks on their use and effectiveness.

The practice of reconditioning or relabeling of consignments after division / merger and/or treatment can complicate the traceability of plants and plant products and may make traceability more difficult to achieve.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

Requirements for the realisation of some tasks or activities in registered and approved premises can be found in the Annexes of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC related to the import and to the introduction of consignments into some Protected Zones.

Annex IVAI 16.2. establishes requirements for the introduction of fruits of *Citrus* L., *Fortunella* Swingle, *Poncirus* Raf., and their hybrids, originating in third countries. When consignments are not introduced from a Pest Free Country or a Pest Free Area, a set of requirements establishes provisions for the field of production, for the fruits and for the packaging premises of the producer or of a registered dispatching centre:

“... (c) either,

- in accordance with an official control and examination regime, no symptoms of *Xanthomonas campestris* (all strains pathogenic to *Citrus*) have been observed in the field of production and in its immediate vicinity since the beginning of the last cycle of vegetation
- and
- none of the fruits harvested in the field of production has shown symptoms of *Xanthomonas campestris* (all strains pathogenic to *Citrus*),
- and
- the fruits have been subjected to treatment such as sodium orthophenylphenate, mentioned on the certificates referred to in Articles 7 or 8 of this Directive,

and
the fruits have been packed at premises or dispatching centres registered for this purpose,
or
— any certification system, recognised as equivalent to the above provisions in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 18(2), has been complied with.”

Requirements for premises with approved waste disposal facilities are included in Annex IV B of the Council Directive. They concern the movement to protected zones of potato tubers not intended for planting (20.2.) and plants for planting of different genera of vegetables and *Brassica* spp. (22.).

The implementation of this RRO is also included as requirement in several EU emergency measures. An exhaustive example of the implementation of this supporting measure is given in the Commission implementing Decision 2016/715/EU concerning the import in EU of *Citrus* fruits from certain Third Countries in order to prevent the introduction of *Phyllosticta citricarpa*, causal agent of Citrus Black Spot disease (CBS)³. This decision was taken with two different objectives, both achieved with requirements related to traceability and official approval of premises:

- 1) to enhance the protection of the EU territory from the introduction of CBS from some Third Countries (Brazil, Uruguay and South Africa) in view of the high number of recurrent interceptions of this pest on *Citrus* fruits originating from there ;
- 2) to allow the introduction of fruits intended for industrial transformation from Third Countries under less strict requirements than those established by the Council Directive 2000/29/EC.

In order to achieve the first objective, the requirements detailed in Annex IVAI 16.4.(c) and (d) (absence of symptoms in the field, in its vicinity and on the fruits harvested, or treatment of the field and absence of symptoms on the fruit harvested) are replaced by provisions of Articles 4, 5 and 6 associated to the additional requirements on traceability of Article 7:

“For traceability purposes, the specified fruits shall be introduced into the Union only if they fulfil the following conditions:

- (a) the field of production, the packing facilities, exporters and any other operator involved in the handling of the specified fruits have been officially registered for that purpose;
- (b) throughout their movement, from the field of production to the point of entry to the Union, the specified fruits have been accompanied by documents issued under the supervision of the National Plant Protection Organisation;
- (c) in the case of the specified fruits originating in South Africa and Uruguay, in addition to points (a) and (b), detailed information on the pre- and post-harvest treatments has been kept. ”

In the case of fruit intended for the industrial processing, considering the lower level of risk of pest introduction associated with this use, the provisions of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC are replaced by the less stringent requirements of the decision 2016/715/EU for *Citrus* fruits movement, processing, storage, containers, packages and labelling. In particular, Article 15 of this decision establishes requirements for the processing of the fruits imported defining the location of the premises, their official registration and approval by the NPPO, the waste management and the obligations in term of traceability:

“1. The specified fruits shall be processed into juice at premises situated in an area where no citrus fruit is produced. The premises shall be officially registered and approved for that purpose by the responsible official body of the Member State in which the premises are situated.

³ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2016/715 of 11 May 2016 setting out measures in respect of certain fruits originating in certain third countries to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Union of the harmful organism *Phyllosticta citricarpa* (McAlpine) Van der Aa.

2. Waste and by-products of the specified fruits shall be used or destroyed in the territory of the Member State where those fruits have been processed in an area where no citrus fruit is produced.
3. The waste and by-products shall be destroyed by deep burial or used by a method approved by the responsible official body of the Member State where the specified fruits have been processed and under the supervision of that official body, in a way to prevent any potential risk for spreading of *Phyllosticta citricarpa*.
4. The processor shall keep records of the specified fruits that are processed and make them available to the responsible official body of the Member State where the specified fruits have been processed. Those records shall indicate the numbers and distinguishing marks of containers, the volumes of the specified fruits imported, the volumes of waste and by-products used or destroyed and detailed information on their use or destruction. "

The implementation of this RRO may represent some technical difficulties and additional work for the stakeholders concerned, in particular for small producers or enterprises, and for the NPPO in charge of the setting out of standards (ISPM 5, 2016) and of the realisation of periodical controls on the reliability of the systems in place.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

The association of control and supporting measures to maintain a Pest Free Area leads to similar effects in terms of reduction of the pest abundance, with a higher level of guarantee than the association of this supporting measure with control measures aimed to achieve a Pest Free Production Place/Site/Consignment.

For some pests, control measures as chemical or physical treatment of the consignments may lead to similar results.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

As supporting measure this risk reduction option leads to the limitation of the pest abundance only when associated to other supporting measures (in particular inspection) and to control measures (use of pest free plant material, effective treatment to the pest concerned, waste management, hygiene of facilities and machinery, etc.) in order to develop phytosanitary strategies such as Pest Free Production Place/Site/Consignment.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO.

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combinations
Pest or vector / plants and plant products.	Production, conditioning and trading premises.	Support of risk reduction options reducing the pest abundance through the whole chain of production and trading.	Complexity of the system for small operators Difficulty to ensure traceability after consignment division, reassembling and reconditioning.	Control and supporting measures associated to guaranty Pest Free Area/ Production Place/Production Site/Consignment.

References

- ISPM 5, 2016. Glossary of phytosanitary terms. International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC), FAO, Rome.
- ISPM 7, 2011. Phytosanitary certification system. International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC), FAO, Rome.